

Developing big-book literacy media as reading learning media for first graders

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Abstract

This research develops big-book literacy media and analyze the media reliability. The method was research and development, using Thiagarajan's model design, i.e., the 4-D model. This model was composed of four phases, namely Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. The developed big-book literacy media was given a reliability percentage of 100% by media experts. The media, accordingly, was categorized as very reliable. It was given a reliability percentage of 92% by language experts, and as such, was considered very reliable as well. Practitioners/users gave a reliability percentage of 98%, classifying the media as very reliable. By accumulating the reliability percentages given by media experts, language experts, and practitioners/users, we could infer that the developed media had a mean reliability percentage of 96.7%, predicating it as a very reliable one. Based on the results of validation and school test, we could declare that the developed big-book literacy media was very reliable to use in a learning process at elementary schools. Grounded on the test using two data collection techniques, which were observation and interviews with teachers and students as users in this test, we could sum up that the developed big-book literacy media was reliable to use in a learning process.

Keywords: Literacy Media; Big Book; Reading; First graders

1. Introduction

It is incumbent upon teachers to apply suitable learning strategies or methods, approaches, media, and sources in a learning environment. A successful learning process can be identified from success levels related to learning objective achievement. An achieved learning objective indicates teacher success in teaching. Learning effectiveness is hence determined by interaction between the components.

In a learning process, teachers have to be concerned about student reading skills. If students have no skills in reading, they will likely meet difficulties during the learning process. Reading skills at early education play a critical role as it acts as the early foundation or the determinant of successful learning activities of students. Student reading skills must be honed, developed since they start their early education, and improved in elementary schools, in which the improvement will be prioritized during their first, second, and third grades. Reading skill improvement at an elementary school level is implemented aligned with grades, i.e., reading for beginning for a lower grade and reading for understanding for a higher one (Ristiana et al., 2021).

Students belonging to these grades need special attention related to their reading skills, as successful learning in these grades is crucial for them. As a beginning step, teachers can determine a suitable reading type attuned to student competencies. Reading for beginning is the suitable reading type for first graders because they start with simple readings. Students are guided to learn a text in a reading containing simple sentences. Reading for beginning requires

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students as beginner readers to pronounce alphabets, read alphabet combination into a syllable, and read syllable combination into a simple word (Muzdalifah & Subrata, 2022). Teaching and developing student reading skills are best carried out using certain learning media, considering that it can assist teachers to manifest meaningful learning and draw student attention to learn to read.

Learning media functions to deliver learning messages from senders (teachers) to recipients (students). If teachers can deliver information effectively to students, and if students can receive the information well, the learning process will run as expected. In so doing, to bring about effective and efficient communication during a learning process, effective communication tools or learning media are needed to fine-tune communication between senders and recipients.

Learning media play an essential role in the learning process conducted by teachers and students. Professional teachers should be able to design effective learning which covers developing and using a range of learning media to engender optimum learning outcomes of students. In designing a learning process, teachers have to develop learning media which can augment the quality of the learning process implemented. A learning process will be effective if the learning objects or materials could be visualized concretely, making them ostensibly real. Students indirectly receive a stimulus when learning using this visualization. Within a teaching-learning context, learning media brings information specifically designed to attain an objective (Johan & Ghasya, 2018).

One of the learning media suitable for developing student reading skills is a big book. Big books are effective for lower-grade students. These big-sized books are favored by children in that they are featured with colorful pictures, simple stories, and reading materials with large fonts. Big books enable the entire class can observe pictures and words when teachers are reading the words to them. Needless to say, big books, namely big-sized books for children, can deliver messages to students and be used in reading lessons.

These big-book media have several features: a) large-size fonts and pictures, helping the entire class to observe them efficiently, b) compact and clear material presentation, c) a variety of colors which can attract students, and d) simple reading texts, unburdening for students and encouraging them to read and understand the reading content (Rulfiariani & Sukidi, 2018).

Our preliminary observation demonstrated that Dewi Jayanti, S.Pd., the homeroom teacher of first graders Sekolah Dasar Laboratorium Universitas Negeri Gorontalo, never used big-book literacy media and was unfamiliar with it. She used pictures and videos presenting alphabets, syllables, or stories as learning media in the learning process which developed student reading skills. She additionally used a learning module on a daily basis. Most first graders could read. 20 out of 24 first graders could read, whereas four others could not. That being so, this big book literacy media is imperative to help her in the learning process.

The teacher thus has to create and use various and innovative learning media, e.g., big books, to draw student attention and focus, foster them to learn, and elevate their learning interest and motivation, specifically related to reading skills.

2. Methods

This research used the research-and-development method to generate a certain product and test the product effectiveness (Sugiyono, 2013). Bord & Gall, in Hamzah (2021), defined research and development as a process of developing and validating existing products, developing new ones, or discovering knowledge or solving problems confronted.

Thiagarajan's model design, i.e., the 4-D model, was used. This model comprised four phases, namely Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate.

This research on developing big-book literacy media for the reading skills of first graders began in August 2022 and ended in May 2023. The research area was SD Laboratorium UNG on Jl. Drs. Achmad Nadjamuddin No. 35, Limba U Dua, Kota Selatan, Gorontalo City. The subjects were the first grader teacher and first graders, consisting of eight male and 16 female students.

Data were collected by observation, interviews, and documentation. Data acquired from this research were data from media experts, language experts, practitioners and collected by distributing assessment instruments concerning the quality of the developed and tested learning media. Data from the validation by media experts, language experts, and practitioners and test results guided us to analyze reliability of the developed media.

Figure 1 The 4-D Model Phases

3. Results and discussion

This research induced a product, which was big-book literacy media for reading skills. It was conducted on first graders SD Laboratorium Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. Thiagarajan's model design, i.e., the 4-D model, was used. This model was made up of four phases: Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate.

3.1. Phase I: Define

Phase I, define, contained an activity of determining the developed product and its specifications. Phase 1 also contained a need analysis performed through research and literature studies (Sugiyono, 2016:38). The analysis was important to examine the field condition and learning needs of the school in connection with learning media it used. Predicated on Phase 1 results and the results of interview with the teacher and learning process observation, we noticed a lack of learning media available for first graders, bringing on monotonous learning media. The teacher often used pictures, videos, word cards, or available learning modules as learning media for student reading skills. There was no other media used. Honing student reading skills had to use attractive learning media as it was widely known that students were disinclined to read if considering the reading materials unattractive. This research, therefore, developed big-book literacy media. This big-book literacy media was interesting to use because of its features which could buoy and assist teachers in the learning process, especially in relation to improving student reading skills. Among the features were big-size texts and pictures, which enabled the entire class to observe them together, attractive color ranges, and simple and attractive reading texts, making students feel unburdened when instructed to read and understand the reading content (Rulfiariani & Sukidi, 2018:630).

3.2. Phase II: Design

Phase II, Design, contained an activity of making the design of the determined and analyzed product. Phase II activity was carried out to design the learning media (Sugiyono, 2016:38). Phase II encompassed determining an attractive reading topic and story content/reading materials included in the big book and determining the media layout, including colorful pictures or illustrations, background selection, characters, fonts, and the big-book media size. We used Canva in laying out each page of the big book.

3.3. Phase III: Develop

Phase III, develop, contained an activity of developing the design into a product, i.e., big-book learning media. After the product development, we conducted validation using instruments, requested the contribution of media experts, language experts, and users/practitioners, and tested the product (Sugiyono, 2016:38). Media experts gave a reliability percentage of 100%, thereby categorizing the product as very reliable, and language experts gave 92%, classifying the

product as very reliable as well. Users/practitioners gave a reliability percentage of 98%, and the product was thus considered very reliable.

Table 1 Recapitulated Results of Validation by Validators

No.	Validator	Results of the Validation of the Big-Book Literacy Media for Student Reading Skills	
		Mean	Criteria
1	Media experts	100	Very Reliable
2	Language experts	92	Very Reliable
3	Practitioners/users	98	Very Reliable
	Total	290	
	Mean = $\frac{\text{Total score}}{\text{Number of validators}}$	96.7	Very Reliable

Table 1 demonstrates the recapitulated results of the validation of the developed big-book literacy media for student reading skills, which exhibited a very reliable criterion. The accumulated results indicated a mean of 96.7 with a validation criterion of very reliable.

We tested the product after expert validation. This test was performed on first graders at SD Laboratorium Universitas Negeri Gorontalo on Thursday, May 4th, 2023. This test was undertaken to investigate the process of using big-book media and efficiency levels in terms of the use. We applied data collection techniques of observation and interview with the teacher and students.

Figure 2 points out the whole appearance of the big-book literacy media after revision.

Our observation of the test presented results that the teacher could use our big-book media efficiently and correctly, and the media could help them listen well when the teacher was reading the story in the big-book media loudly. Students responded actively and enthusiastically to the teacher's questions during the answer-question session. They could understand the story content well and understand the language used in the big-book media, making them able to learn new vocabulary in either the Gorontalo language or English. And yet, students could not read English readings and only listened to them. Reading the big-book media in turn, students showed interest and enthusiasm as the media used large fonts.

We interviewed the first-grade teacher after testing the big-book media. She admitted that our big-book literacy media answered student needs related to the learning process and that the media could help students during the learning process, particularly when reading. Students read the big-book media happily and learned enthusiastically in that the activity was new to them. The media contained pictures, which prevented students from feeling bored, like when they read texts only. Realistic pictures the media was featured with enabled students to listen and read the stories more enthusiastically. In addition, the size and attractive color of the media made students interested in learning. The stories were attractive and understandable for students. The diction, which was in the Gorontalo language, was understandable and readable for students. The large size fonts enabled students to read the media easily.

We also interviewed students aside from interviewing the teacher. During the interview, students argued that stories contained by the big-book media were attractive, not to mention the large font it used, making them happy and interested in reading it. The media contained colorful and attractive pictures. They showed enthusiasm and were very happy when observing and using the big-book media. Based on the results of the test, observation, and interview with the teacher and students as users in this test, we could declare that the developed big-book literacy media was reliable and could be used in the learning process.

Figure 2 The Appearance of the Big-Book Media After Revision

3.4. Phase IV: Disseminate

In phase IV, Disseminate, we disseminated the tested product and allowed others to use it (Sugiyono, 2016:38). The product was ready to use after being validated by experts, acquiring a positive score, and considered reliable to use. After being assessed through expert validation and tested, this developed big-book literacy media was reliable and could be used in the learning process. The big-book media was distributed to first graders, who then used it in the learning process. This research was published in the form of an undergraduate thesis and an article in the SINTA journal, enabling readers to refer from it.

4. Conclusion

This developed product was validated by experts, i.e., media experts, language experts, practitioners/users using validation instruments. The product was given a reliability percentage of 100% by media experts and accordingly, was categorized as very reliable. It was given a reliability percentage of 92% by language experts and as such, was classified as very reliable as well. Users/practitioners gave it a reliability percentage of 98%. It was also considered very reliable based on the reliability percentage of 98% given by users/practitioners. Grounded on the recapitulated validation results, the developed big-book literacy media for student reading skills was very reliable to use. The accumulated result was 96.7 on average with the validation criterion of very reliable. Predicated on the test carried out using data collection techniques of observation and interviews with the teacher and students as users in this test, the developed big-book literacy media was reliable and could be used in the learning process.

Suggestion

We suggest that teachers create and use more various and innovative learning media to attract students, help them focus on learning, especially to support their reading skills, motivate them, and make them more enthusiastic, active, and focused on partaking in the learning process.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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